

TRENDS IN PUBLIC EXPENDITURE FOR KARNATAKA- AN ANALYSIS

Varsha. N

*Research Scholar, Department of Economics, Jnana Bharathi Campus, Bangalore University,
Bengaluru – 560056.*

Dr. N Rangaswamy

*Professor (Retd), Department of Economics, Jnana Bharathi Campus, Bangalore University,
Bengaluru -560056.*

Abstract:

Karnataka is a medium-spending state and has seen stagnation in its overall government expenditure as a percentage of GSDP. While the literature highlights that excessive government expenditure is detrimental to the overall economic prosperity of the economy, the reduction in expenditure in certain areas warrants greater analysis. It has been found that while both revenue and capital expenditure have been stagnating for the Karnataka government, the share of education expenditure in revenue expenditure has witnessed a decline, and expenditure towards fiscal services and pensions has increased. On the capital front, greater spending has been on transport, irrigation, and flood control. There also has been an increase in expenditure on housing (rural and urban). This study presents the trends in the expenditure pattern experienced by the Karnataka state over the period 2004-05 to 2019-20 (BE). The main objective of this study is to understand the movements observed in the total as well as the components of the State's expenditure and to highlight the changes observed.

Keywords: Public Expenditure, Fiscal Services, and GSDP.

Introduction

The Economic Development of any country depends on many factors, among them public expenditure is considered an important instrument to accentuate the Growth of the Economy. The role of public expenditure in a free-hand economy plays a critical role. Public expenditure is a vast source of information depicting the spending characteristics of the government. Expenditure, which in essence is the cost of input, is said to be productive if it has the desired effect, i.e., towards the production of output. In the case of government expenditure, the aim is to enhance economic growth and public welfare. It creates infrastructure both in the physical and human capital which is assumed to produce unprecedented growth of the economy.

According to the Budget Manual for Karnataka State, total expenditure is the sum of revenue and capital expenditure and this expenditure is made from the Consolidated Fund of the State Government. Revenue expenditure is the expenditure made from revenue receipts (such as from taxes and duties, fees for services, fines, and penalties, etc.) under the revenue account and is also termed as current expenditure. These expenditures are concurring in nature and include items such as salaries and pensions, payment of interests, etc. Capital expenditure arises out of the capital account and is made to increase construction or procure physical assets (capital assets), such as buildings, roads, irrigation projects, etc. These assets may or may not have revenue generation capacity. The expenditures under this category are met out of receipts other than revenue in nature, such as loans, sale of bonds, public debt, etc. These usually include lump-sum payments and are not recurrent in nature.

Further, the revenue and capital expenditures are divided into three categories of expenditure, based on the functions of the government general services, economic services, and social services. Expenditures under general services are essential to

maintain the state machinery, such as expenditures towards the functioning of the organs of the State, salaries and pensions, administrative services, etc. Economic services include activities that promote the economic activities in the economy, such as expenditure towards agriculture and allied activities, irrigation and flood control, transport, etc. Social services are expenditures towards enhancing human capital and improving social welfare, such as expenditure towards education, health care, water, sanitation, etc.

Review of Literature:

Ghosh and Prabir (2004) in this paper the researchers investigate the role played by various types of infrastructure facilities in determining the level of economic development across Indian states in the period of 1970-71 to 1999-2000. The major findings are interstate disparity in physical, social and financial infrastructural facilities have remained at high level over the same period and physical and social infrastructure facilities highly significant factors determining the interstate level of development, while financial infrastructure dose not play clear role

Shiddalingaswami and Raghavendra (2010) In this paper the authors analyze the trends and pattern of per capita income of Karnataka with special focus on district and division level disparities and also study the relationship among and between per capita income, human development, workforce and work participation rate from 1991 to 2007-08. The major finding of the study is social overhead capital (SOC) is key factor in promoting higher and economic development, which will reduce the regional disparity.

Objectives:

1. To examine the trends in government expenditure for Karnataka.
2. To know the growth and performance of different components of public expenditure in Karnataka.

Trends in Government Expenditure for Karnataka

The report analyses the trends in government expenditure and its components over the past period from 2004-05 to 2019-20 (BE) to highlight the shifts in expenditure patterns and bring the reasons for the same. Figure 1 depicts the total government expenditure comprising revenue and capital for Karnataka for the period 2004-05 to 2019-20 (BE).

Figure 1: Government Expenditure as a percentage of GSDP, 2004-05 to 2019-20, Karnataka

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years) and Directorate of Economics and Statistics (Karnataka).

It can be observed that the percentage of total expenditure to GSDP was nearly 18 percent during 2004-05 to 2011-12, post which there has been a decline and has stagnated at 13 per cent of GSDP. There has been a constant effort by the State government to limit its expenditure.

Figure 2 depicts the movements in the component of total expenditure, viz., revenue and capital as a percentage of GSDP. The figure highlights that revenue expenditure is greater than capital expenditure. Both the revenue and capital expenditure shows a decline from 2004-05 to 2011-12 and stabilize post-2012-13. As the revenue expenditure is nearly 80 per cent of the total expenditure (Figure 3), the total expenditure largely mimics the movements observed in it. The high share of revenue expenditure is because capital expenditure does not include disbursements from public debt, loans and advances, and other capital outlay items.

Figure 2: Revenue and capital expenditure as a percentage of GSDP, 2004-05 to 2019-20, Karnataka

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years) and Directorate of Economics and Statistics (Karnataka).

The total revenue and capital expenditure patterns highlight that Karnataka’s expenditure is heavily skewed towards revenue expenditure and the proportion has not significantly changed. Also, there has been stagnation in the recent past, as the share of these expenditures to the state GSDP has not varied substantially.

Figure 3: Share of revenue and capital expenditure in total expenditure, 2004-05 to 2019-20, Karnataka.

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years) and Directorate of Economics and Statistics(Karnataka)

In Figures 4 and 5, revenue and capital expenditure are further classified into general, economic, and social services respectively.

Figure 4: General, economic, and social services as percentages of revenue expenditure, 2004- 05 to 2019-20, Karnataka.

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years).

It can be observed in Figure 4 that there has been a gradual increase in social services-related expenditure since 2004-05. Unlike in the case of capital expenditure (Figure 5), where 80 percent of the capital expenditure is directed towards economic services, there is a more even distribution among the three services in the case of revenue expenditure. Another feature of the composition of revenue expenditure has been that while the social expenditure has risen, there has been a gradual decline in the share of general services from 2004-05.

Figure 5: General, economic, and social services as percentages of capital expenditure, 2004- 05 to 2019-20, Karnataka.

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years).

As general services are mostly revenue in nature, they do not feature prominently in the capital expenditure. It can be observed from Figure 5 that after 2012-13, the social services has depicted a slight increase in its share which is accompanied by a decline in economic services. In the following, the analysis depicts the movements across the components of functional expenditures. The trends in expenditures observed across the components of general, economic, and social services under revenue and capital expenditures are presented below.

Revenue expenditure

Figures 6, 7, and 8 present the trends across the general, economic, and social services under the revenue expenditure. The trends are depicted for the main components which have the highest share under the respective services.

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years).

The administrative expenditure has witnessed a gradual decline in the share of revenue expenditure. Pension and other compensations have surged post-2009-10, after the implementation of the Revised Pay Commission. Fiscal services such as interest payments along with organs of the state have remained stagnant. It can be observed that in the general services, fiscal services have the highest share of around 40 per cent and the lowest is towards the maintenance of organs of the state.

Under the economic services, the two main activities that control nearly 60 percent of the revenue expenditure are agriculture and allied activities and energy provisioning services. Figure 7 depicts that during 2014-15, there was a peak in the resources assigned to the agriculture sector. This was to compensate for the losses to the sector during crop failures. The “others” include rural development and transport, whose shares have remained at 10 and 9 percent respectively.

Figure7: Components of economic services in revenue expenditure, 2004-05 to 2019-20, Karnataka

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years).

Figure 8 presents the trend in the components of social services under the revenue expenditure account. It can be observed that education and other curricular activities have witnessed a decline since 2004-05. A rise in “others” is primarily on account of rising expenditure on water, sanitation, and housing under social services.

Figure 8: Components of social services in revenue expenditure, 2004-05 to 2019 20, Karnataka.

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years).

Capital expenditure

Under the capital expenditure, the analysis focuses on economic services as they constitute a majority of the expenditure made under the capital account. Figure 9 depicts the same. Irrigation expenditure has decreased from 80 per cent of total economic services to 50 per cent in recent times. The increase in transport expenditure has been primarily on roads and bridges and roads.

Figure9: Components of economic services in capital expenditure, 2004-05 to 2019-20, Karnataka

Source: Accounts at a Glance, Karnataka (Various Years).

Among general services, the police held 60 percent of the share whereas, public works held 40 per cent during 2004-05, which changed to a police holding 33 percent and public works holding 67 per cent during 2019-20 respectively. Among social services water, sanitation, housing, and urban development held the maximum share in 2004-05 (at 87 per cent). This has been reduced to 38 percent by 2018-19 (RE). This has been due to the increase in spending towards SC/ST/OBC welfare and education.

The trends analysis of the expenditure pattern of the Karnataka state has brought out a few interesting points. There has been stagnation in the overall expenditure as a percentage of GSDP, but delving into the components of the expenditure suggests that under the revenue expenditure, a large share of resources are put into fiscal services and pensions and compensation. Also, there has been a decline in education and allied expenditure which does not bode well for the state’s development. At the same time, the state has maintained a low share of expenditure on the organs of the state and administrative services. Under the capital expenditure, economic services directed

towards the creation of new assets for irrigation and transport has dominated the expenditure pattern. These according to economic literature are considered productive investments and have a strong push for economic growth in the state.

Conclusion

The study has analyzed the role of government expenditure on economic growth in the presence of institutional quality as well as the productivity of government expenditure, both labour, and capital at the national and state level.

The main conclusions from the trends analysis suggest that in Karnataka, there has been stagnation in the level of government expenditure. Both revenue and capital expenditures have stagnated since 2011-12. Among the revenue expenditure components, the reduction in education-related revenue expenditure is worrisome. Similarly, the rise in pensions could also pose long-run problems in curtailing non-productive expenditure. A decline in education expenditure must be corrected as it is essential for the development of human capital, which is directly linked with economic prosperity and welfare.

It was also found that states with higher physical capital have higher growth rates. Thus, the promotion of investments in physical capital yields a positive impact on income levels in the states. The panel analysis also found a strong positive link between institutions and economic growth. Thus, care must be given to developing and strengthening the institutional framework in the states. Importance must be given to health care, education, access to safe water and sanitation facilities, etc.

In the productivity analysis at the state and national level, it was found that the overall productivity of labour at the state and national level was stagnant, whereas the productivity of capital has been increasing. This further suggests that governments need to develop physical capital for better utilization of resources in the economy at the

national and state levels. One of the reasons why Karnataka performs better in terms of labour and capital productivity in the government and private sector could be the presence of stronger institutions when compared to many other states.

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